

MESS 0004

The Rapid Growth of the EPEMC Tree: a review of EPEMC evolution

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ABSTRACT

The EPEMC¹ tree is now MESSy², and as such a brief review of the previously discussed evolutionary stages is warranted. Furthermore, other researchers may find the thinktanks (Pulse³ & AIM⁴), movements (SPACERS⁵, MIMS⁶), and other regions of work either gratifying or sorely lacking, based on evolution of the cosmology, of the Author, or both. Real science enables free and open exchange of doubt and critique, so honesty is encouraged in an open-source format. See the EPEMC Standards⁷ and Volunteer⁸ pages for more information, as well as “Why to Switch to EPEMC”⁹ and “How to Create a MIMS”¹⁰ documents. Also recommended are the memos¹¹ and FAQs¹².

Keywords: Plasma-Electromagnetic-cosmology-Philosophy-Science-Standards

¹ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC

² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims/mess>

³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/home/shows>

⁴ AIM - Advanced Idea Mechanics - Planning Document

⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/mims>

⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer>

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https://www.academia.edu/37569958/EPEMC_tm_Benefits_Ten_Reasons_to_Consider_Switching_to_Extended_Plasma_electromagnetic_Cosmology

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How_to_Create_a_MIMS

¹¹

https://www.academia.edu/40069702/The_Electric_Universe_Memo_For_Plasma_Electromagnetic_and_Diffusion_Catastrophic_Cosmologies_EPEMC_An_Electric_View_Community_Publication

¹² https://www.academia.edu/50912946/FAQ_EPEMC_MIMS

EPEMC - the Author's Evolution

The Author has the following basic origin "story":

Figure 1 - A life of evolution, 1983-2022; credit: author

As one can see, after a lifetime of Truth-Pursuit, there is a lot of finding of new data that did not, cannot, fit into the small jar that is provided to children in the West today. This is a common experience.

EPEMC - the Cosmology's Evolution

With the birth of EPEMC (and denial by the author to take up an invitation to join Master Josh Paynter's¹³ Thunder Magik sect), the journey through Electric Universe into our joint history *began*. EPEMC is a combination of three things:

- ❖ Combined (matrix mediated¹⁴) fractal (non-linear) views of plasma cosmology and classical EM
- ❖ Cross-disciplinary sciences
- ❖ Comparative Mythology

¹³ <https://www.amazon.com/Joshua-M-Paynter/e/B07ZFTR8JH>

¹⁴ [the Truth]_(within X context)

The result is a *tree* of pathways, which shows lots of types of growth both within the author and especially within the EPEMC. The deeper the *current* of truth found, the more power the growth has, and the more rapidity. It may turn out to be a whole forest, rather than a single tree, but for now we will visualize it up-down:

Key: cubes are products/tools, the diamonds are standards, and the hexagons are shows/podcasts.

Summary

The inputs of the “Art of Chess,” Bagua Dharma (and ergo Triple Plane theory, TPT), and “Qi as Scalar Waves” has led to many developments in the EPEMC open-source paradigm. To date, the worst criticism received was that the myths were being taken too literally, but there were no replies about the core of EPEMC theory: the LiDAR evidence, the plasmaglyphic forensics, the cross-cultural morphologies, the ratios and probability calculations, etc. In short the hypothesis grows unstoppably, and the theories relatively unmolested. The reason this matters is that the AIM standard encourages massive scaling, as does MESSiness. In other words, “this is about to blow up.”